

The Status of Changing Education Program and Innovating Teaching Methods for Elementary Teachers in Viet Nam

Bui Van Van

The University of Da Nang – University of Science and Education

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ABSTRACT

The Ministry of Education and Training has issued Circular No. 32/2018/TTBTC dated December 26, 2018 on the general education program, which has been implemented from the school year 2020-2021 starting from grade 1 and moving on to the next grade. The Ministry of Education and Training, as well as educational management organizations, have undertaken numerous actions in order to prepare for the General Education Program's promulgation and implementation in 2018. There are numerous challenges for teachers, students, parents, and administrators at this period of change in the educational program, particularly in terms of employing new teaching methods for kids. Collaboration between families, schools, and students is essential. In this article, we examine studies on the changing situation of educational programs in Vietnam, as well as the challenges of innovating teaching techniques and providing creative teaching methods for primary school instructors during this time.

Corresponding author:
Bui Van Van

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1. INTRODUCTION

The goal and structure of Vietnam's educational system are changing for the better, but there are still many obstacles ahead. On the one hand, the entire society is protesting the inadequacies that education has failed to address; on the other hand, the education sector is being compelled to alter and change policies and programs in order to keep up with regional and international progress at the same time. These issues must be rectified right now.

In Vietnam's education and training system, modernizing teaching methods is a pressing concern. Our country's education will be renewed synchronously, fundamentally, and comprehensively by 2020, according to the "Education Development Strategy from 2010-2020". Emphasizing that addressing the problem of teaching innovation will transform the way teachers teach, the way students learn, stimulate student activity, and improve the quality of education in schools. Primary education is regarded as the cornerstone of general education as well as the development of future citizen personalities.

The 8th Plenum of the 11th Central Committee passed Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW on November 4, 2013, which stated: "Strongly moving the educational process from primarily equipping knowledge to holistic development of learner's potential and quality. Continually innovating

teaching and learning approaches in the direction of modernity; promoting learner optimism, initiative, creativity, and application of knowledge and skills; overcoming one-way imposing transmission, remembering little rationale". In accordance with this resolution, the Ministry of Education and Training formally announced the General Education Program on December 27, 2018, which clearly demonstrates the program's evolution in light of the formation and development strategy. Students' quality and capacity should be improved. As a result, the teaching method has been updated to emphasize development.

2. THE CURRENT STATE OF INNOVATION IN TEACHING METHODS

According to research by Thai, D. T. (2008) and Nguyen, A.N (2019), several contents of management of innovative teaching strategies based on students' competency approach are not successfully utilized, for example: There is a dearth of preparation and checking, and everything isn't centered. Connell CJ, Endacott R, Jackman JA, Kiprillis NR, Sparkes LM, Cooper SJ (2016) show, teachers' capacity has not matched the demands of education and training innovation, and there have been few training subjects for teachers to carry out teaching in the direction of improving students' capacity, despite the concerns of leaders at all levels.

In addition, Nguyen, T.M.L (2012) and et. show some teachers are inactive, slow to adapt to changes, and have limited capacity to apply information technology and apply modern teaching methods; the examination and evaluation of students' learning results still focuses on evaluating subjects by scores, not paying attention to assessing students' learning process; the fostering of self-study methods, the activeness and initiative of students in self-seeking and discovering knowledge have not been paid attention, resulting in the lack of activeness, creativity, and passivity in lessons (Nguyen T. T. D., 2018) and Do, T.T.Thuy, 2017).

Research results by Le, T.K.T, Nguyen, T.H (2019), on the perception of administrators and teachers about the role of innovating teaching methods in primary schools in Bien Hoa city, Dong Nai province shows that most administrators and teachers assessed it's important (management staff: 40%; teachers: 59.2%) and very important (management staff: 40%; teachers: 22.1%), only a few rated at relatively important and very few is not important.

According to Nguyen, T. H. and Nguyen, T. B. P (2019) research, administrators and instructors in primary schools are aware of how to develop teaching approaches: Primary school administrators and teachers in Quang town Tri recognized the importance of creative teaching methods. Teachers and 98.7% of management personnel believe that teaching method innovation is "essential" or higher (26.6 percent "necessary", and 72.1% "very necessary"). This is a correct perspective because one of the most necessary and crucial contents in educational activities at schools is inventing teaching methods in order to achieve a quality breakthrough and meet the needs of educational innovation. Currently, the findings reveal that "innovation of teaching methods is important," knowing that administrators and instructors chose the "agree" choice at the highest level.

Nguyen, T., Nguyen T. K. T. (2016) and Ta, T.H; Phan, V. Q.; Ngo, T. Y. (2016) show that: Some approaches to regulate the innovation of teaching methods in elementary schools with the goal of enhancing students' abilities is:

Increasing administrators' and teachers' understanding of innovative teaching strategies that lead to student capacity development

Innovating and designing lesson plans in order to increase students' abilities through innovative teaching methods

Directing the professional group's operations to be renewed in accordance with the policy of strengthening student capability through innovative teaching approaches.

Organizing some training for teachers to help them develop innovative teaching strategies that will help students become better teachers.

Directing teachers to encourage students' learning styles in the direction of capacity development.

Strengthening the guidance, testing, and evaluation of new teaching methods used by teachers in the development of students' abilities.

The current status of managing activities of nurturing primary school teachers in Krong Nang district, Dak Lak province, according to research by Do.V.L and Tran V. H (2020), demonstrates that a portion of management personnel and instructors are aware of the position and responsibility of teachers. The role and importance of teacher education are not high, as evidenced by the lack of regular and synchronous teacher education work in some schools; the use of supporting conditions for fostering has been concerned by managers and principals, but not to the extent that it should be; and the schools have not actively developed the teacher education plan, relying heavily on the Department of Education and Training's annual direction plan.

3. ADVISING ON WAYS TO IMPROVE TEACHING METHODS

The World Bank (WB) has committed hundreds of millions of dollars in Vietnam's education, according to authors Nguyen, M. T. (2019), the educational condition in Vietnam remains unsatisfactory which encourage society to continue to criticize.

Vietnam is going through an educational reform period, which is one of the most important strategies to transform the country's face. To put it another way, "reviving education according to life's orders" necessitates the development of innovative teaching approaches at the university level. One of the sad realities to see is that Vietnamese degrees are not fully recognized internationally, and while Vietnamese people in particular have illustrious achievements on five continents, such as winning international awards, the country's educational results in general are still below the global average.

Erica A., N., C. Chris, and A. Sunddip Panesar, (2018), confirm that, Primary school is the first level of education in the general education system, so it is very important to renew teaching methods right from this level. Follow Pham, T. T. T. (2019), principals of primary schools, on the other hand, must be the ones to directly persuade each teacher to modify their awareness and actions in innovative teaching methods in the direction of student competency growth in order to execute this work properly. The article discusses several management strategies for innovating teaching methods in elementary schools in order to improve student competency development.

Basis for proposed measures

- Legal basis: The educational activities of the schools must comply with all kinds of legal documents of the state and the Ministry of Education and Training. These documents are the legal basis for us to propose measures to improve the efficiency of the management of innovative teaching methods in the direction of students' energy development. Specifically:

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+ Law on Education dated June 14, 2005; Law amending and supplementing a number of articles of the Education Law dated November 25, 2009.

+ Decree No. 75/2006/ND-CP dated August 2, 2006 of the Government detailing and guiding the implementation of a number of articles of the Education Law.

+ Resolution No. 29-NQ/TW dated November 4, 2013 on fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training.

+ Resolution No. 88/2014/QH13 dated November 28, 2014 of the National Assembly on Renovating general education curricula and textbooks.

+ Resolution No. 51/2017/QH14 dated November 21, 2017 of the National Assembly adjusting the implementation schedule of new general education programs and textbooks according to Resolution No. 88/2014/QH13 dated November 28, 2014 of the National Assembly on reforming general education curricula and textbooks.

+ Education development strategy 2011-2020 (Promulgated together with Decision No. 711/QD-TTg dated June 13, 2012 of the Prime Minister).

+ Decision No. 404/QD-TTg dated March 27, 2015 of the Prime Minister approving the Scheme on renovation of general education curricula and textbooks.

+ Circular No. 32/2018/TT 26/12/2018 of the Minister of Education and Training on Promulgating the General Education Program.

- Practical basis: Despite the successes in recent years, the administration of innovative teaching methods in the direction of student competency development in primary schools in Vietnam has a long way to go. Specifically:

+ A few departments lack a thorough understanding of the role and meaning of teaching innovation activities, which sometimes leads to formal implementation;

+ Developing a plan to renew teaching methods among disciplines is not synchronized, which causes many difficulties in connecting knowledge between specialties;

+ The management and implementation of innovative teaching methods in accordance with the orientation of student competency development is not synchronized, which causes many difficulties in connecting knowledge between specialties;

+ The goal of "personalization" in teaching has not been achieved in essence, the teacher's approach to student capacity is not suitable for implementing teaching content;

+ The management team's assessment of each stage of planning as well as implementation of the plan is not close to reality;

+ The activities of observing time and visiting classes to contribute ideas and learn from experience are not really effective;

+ Facilities for teaching 2 sessions/day in some schools are still lacking, teaching equipment in each subject is sketchy, and information technology equipment is not good;

+ The environment for organizing experiential learning activities is not professional.

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CONCLUSION

Many teachers used to teach and learn in the classic "read-write" approach, or "quickly teach formulae and rules and then conduct exercises"... Nguyen, V.H. (2017) comments teachers did not focus on learners or have yet to appreciate learners' abilities. It's also possible that professors undervalue their students' abilities. Some teachers appear to avoid large-scale campaigns on teaching methods and rarely adapt their old teaching approaches. We believe that in order to encourage teachers to innovate teaching methods, they must courageously employ new approaches and new ways to understand students' awareness, resulting in improved educational outcomes.

The findings reveal that, in response to the demands of basic and comprehensive education reform in Vietnam, management staff and teachers in primary schools in general have professional qualifications, are excited about their work, and have a positive attitude. converge on the objective of reforming the teaching profession. The foundation for recommending strategies to improve the effectiveness of innovative teaching methods in elementary schools is a correct understanding.

Apart from the flaws, the education industry in Vietnam is through a time of significant development, with many changes and notable achievements. Many minds and hearts have been roused to join the rhythm of education, particularly while conducting several seminars to elicit teacher and scientist comments on school and education concerns. Although there are still many challenges to face in the near

future, we anticipate that Vietnam's education industry will make significant growth in the not-too-distant future.

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